

Drift Simulation Analysis of a Capsized Vessel near Lampedusa

Luca Kunz

Ocean Research and Conservation Luca Kunz, Hamburg, Germany

Correspondence: luca.kunz@orac.earth

12 November 2024

Abstract—On September 4, 2024, the Italian Coast Guard conducted a rescue operation within 12 nautical miles (nmi) off the coast of Lampedusa involving a capsized vessel and several survivors. Two days earlier, on September 2, the vessel and numerous individuals on board were spotted by the crew of the civil monitoring aircraft *Seabird*, operated by the NGO *Sea-Watch e.V.* This report presents findings from oceanographic drift simulations designed to reconstruct the vessel’s trajectory and estimate its entry time into the Italian Search and Rescue (SAR) zone off Lampedusa. Utilising the *OpenDrift* framework, we simulated hypothetical drift paths for the vessel based on prevailing sea surface currents and wind conditions. Our results suggest that the vessel began drifting approximately 75 minutes after the last *Seabird* sighting. Additionally, our simulations indicate that the rescue operation commenced several hours after the vessel likely entered the Italian SAR zone. These findings provide crucial insights into the vessel’s movements and the overall timeline of the incident.

I. INTRODUCTION

On September 2, 2024, the civil monitoring aircraft *Seabird* (SB), operated by the NGO *Sea-Watch e.V.*, spotted a vessel navigating through the Mediterranean Sea, heading towards the island of Lampedusa. The vessel, which was assigned the ID number *DC897*, was observed three times over a few hours, with each sighting showing a large number of people on board. However, by September 4, the vessel was found capsized within 12 nautical miles (nmi) off the coast of Lampedusa, with only a few survivors remaining. The Italian Coast Guard conducted the subsequent rescue operation. Using Open Source Intelligence Tools (OSINT), the SB crew estimated the location of this rescue. They tracked a *Guardia di Finanza* helicopter orbiting over the coordinates 35°24’N, 12°26’E at 09:38 UTC on September 4, and identified this position as the assumed site and time of the rescue.

Reports from survivors, relatives and witnesses have helped reconstruct the sequence of events between the final SB sighting on September 2 and the rescue operation on September 4. According to these accounts, the vessel first capsized about an hour after the third SB sighting on September 2. The boat was subsequently righted, allowing many passengers to climb back on board. However, the boat capsized again, leaving all individuals overboard until the rescue. These

details are essential for understanding the vessel’s activities and movements following the last confirmed sighting. Given the available information, determining the vessel’s drift path and its potential entry into the Italian Search and Rescue (SAR) zone off Lampedusa is critical to establishing the facts surrounding this incident. Accordingly, this report seeks to address two primary research questions:

- 1) **Where could the vessel have drifted if the engine had ceased operation shortly after the third *Seabird* spotting, considering prevailing sea and weather conditions?**
- 2) **When did the vessel likely enter the Italian SAR zone off Lampedusa, the 12 nmi Italian territorial waters off Lampedusa and the estimated rescue zone 5 km around the helicopter sighting?**

To address these questions, we perform a series of Lagrangian drift simulations using the *OpenDrift* framework (Dagestad et al., 2018), an oceanographic tool designed to model the movement of particles on the sea surface. The simulations utilise data about sea surface currents and wind conditions to recreate the vessel’s possible drift paths, considering different scenarios and object types. This report outlines the methodologies employed, presents the results of the simulations, and discusses the potential implications of the findings for understanding the incident’s timeline.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Lagrangian Drift Simulations

Lagrangian drift simulations are a standard oceanographic tool used to estimate the passive transport of objects or substances across the sea surface, such as oil, debris or vessels. In this method, virtual particles are released at specific locations and times, and their movement is tracked over time using data on sea currents and wind patterns. These simulations help predict potential drift paths and are widely employed across different fields:

- 1) **Marine Search and Rescue (SAR):** Drift simulations play a critical role in search and rescue operations to estimate the probable location of drifting vessels, life rafts or persons in water after a distress signal is received. By simulating drift patterns based on real-time oceanographic and meteorological data, rescue teams

can optimise search areas and improve the chances of a successful rescue. Many Coast Guard authorities around the world, including those in the United States and Norway, regularly use Lagrangian particle simulations as part of their emergency response strategies to locate missing vessels and individuals (Øyvind Breivik et al., 2013).

- 2) **Oil Spill Response:** Drift models are essential for predicting the spread of oil spills, allowing environmental agencies to plan and execute containment and clean-up operations. By simulating the drift of oil on the sea surface, responders can assess the potential impact on coastal ecosystems and marine life, facilitating effective mitigation strategies. The 2010 Deepwater Horizon spill in the Gulf of Mexico, for example, employed extensive drift modelling to track the spill's spread (Ainsworth et al., 2021).
- 3) **Marine Debris Tracking:** With growing concerns over plastic pollution, drift simulations help researchers understand how marine debris, such as plastics, disperses across the world's oceans. These models inform efforts to locate high-density accumulation zones, known as "garbage patches", and to design strategies for marine debris collection and reduction. A well-known application is the tracking of floating debris across the Pacific, where simulations have mapped out large accumulation zones (Lebreton et al., 2018).
- 4) **Oceanographic Research and Climate Studies:** Scientists use drift models to study the transport of plankton, nutrients and other biological materials across the ocean. These models help in understanding how ocean currents influence marine ecosystems and can also be used to model the dispersion of pollutants or natural tracers. For instance, recent studies have used drift models to assess the connectivity between marine protected areas and to understand larval dispersal in marine species (Simons et al., 2013).

The versatility of Lagrangian drift models makes them an invaluable tool in maritime operations, environmental protection and scientific research. Given the wide range of applications and the critical importance of accurate drift modelling in maritime operations, selecting an appropriate simulation framework is essential. We have chosen the OpenDrift framework for this analysis due to its proven flexibility and adaptability across various scenarios, including SAR, oil spill response and environmental monitoring. As a widely recognised tool within the oceanographic community, OpenDrift has been successfully used in multiple studies to model complex drift patterns by integrating diverse data sources (Dagestad et al., 2018). In our study, the application of the OpenDrift framework allowed for simulating the vessel's potential drift path from its last known location to the point of rescue, taking into account real-time oceanographic conditions.

B. Simulation Setup

On September 2, 2024, the SB crew sighted the vessel of concern three times, with each observation showing it carrying many people on board. These sightings were accurate

to within less than a minute and a nautical mile, and the information was promptly communicated to the authorities. For the Italian Coast Guard rescue on September 4, the SB crew used Open Source Intelligence Tools (OSINT) to estimate the approximate time and location of the operation. They tracked a Guardia di Finanza helicopter orbiting over the coordinates 35°24'N, 12°26'E at 09:38 UTC, identifying this as the assumed site and time of the rescue.

This information was corroborated by a press release of the Italian Coast Guard locating the rescue operation at around 10 nautical miles southwest of Lampedusa (Guardia Costiera, 2024a). The helicopter orbited over the position from 09:38 UTC until at least 10:07 UTC and is visible in a video of the rescue operation published by the Italian Coast Guard on X (formerly Twitter, Guardia Costiera (2024b)). Testimonies by the survivors further confirm the helicopter's presence during the rescue operation. However, the estimation of the rescue location carries a higher degree of uncertainty compared to the SB sightings, particularly in spatial terms. To account for this, we define the rescue zone as the area within a 5 km radius of the observed helicopter position. The following timeline summarizes the times and coordinates of the vessel sightings, as well as the estimated time and location of the Italian Coast Guard rescue:

- **SB Sighting #1:**
September 2 12:28 UTC at coordinates 34°53'N, 12°37'E
- **SB Sighting #2:**
September 2 13:38 UTC at coordinates 34°59'N, 12°35'E
- **SB Sighting #3:**
September 2 14:40 UTC at coordinates 35°04'N, 12°33'E

- **Rescue Operation (Estimation):**
September 4 09:38 UTC at coordinates 35°24'N, 12°26'E and within a 5 km radius

The interval between the last known position on September 2 and the helicopter sighting on September 4 served as the core period for our drift simulation, enabling us to model the vessel's movements and estimate its likely positions throughout this timeframe. Since the vessel was sighted three times, each time observed to be moving under engine power with an approximately constant bearing, we extrapolated its trajectory based on the vessel's last confirmed direction and speed. Reports from survivors, along with testimonies from relatives of those on board, indicate that the boat capsized shortly after the third sighting. This information was essential for constructing a realistic extrapolation of the times and locations where the vessel may have started to drift.

We initiated simulations from 17 distinct positions to comprehensively explore potential drift scenarios. Beginning at the coordinates of the third sighting, we extrapolated the vessel's trajectory using a constant speed and direction, determining subsequent positions at 15-minute intervals, which corresponds to the temporal resolution of the ocean current velocity data employed in the simulation. We extended the extrapolation to four hours beyond the third sighting, assuming that the engine may have shut down shortly after this last observed location. Each of these extrapolated positions was

sequentially labelled as EXT000, EXT015, EXT030, up to EXT240, with the labels indicating the minutes elapsed since the third sighting. This range of release points was chosen to account for uncertainties regarding the vessel’s status and to ensure that our simulations covered a variety of potential drift starting points. Fig. 1 summarises these details, providing an overview of all sighted and extrapolated vessel positions, the estimated 5 km rescue zone, the 12 nmi boundary of Italian territorial waters around the islands of Lampedusa, Lampione and Linosa, and the surrounding boundaries of the Italian SAR zone.

Figure 1. Overview of the simulation setup. Black markers and labels show the times and coordinates of the three vessel sightings reported by the SB crew. Red markers indicate extrapolated vessel positions, with larger markers denoting full-hour intervals after the last confirmed sighting. At each extrapolated position, 10,000 particles were released for each of the four object types, simulating their drift until September 4 09:40 UTC. The green marker represents the helicopter observation by the SB crew, estimating the centre and time of the Italian Coast Guard rescue, with the rescue area outlined by the green 5 km contour. The black dashed contour marks the 12 nmi territorial waters boundary around Lampedusa, Lampione and Linosa. The blue contour indicates the surrounding limits of the Italian SAR zone.

Key elements of the simulation setup included:

- **Data Sources:** We utilised high-resolution ocean surface current velocity data with a temporal resolution of 15 minutes and spatial resolution of $1/24^\circ$ (CMEMS, 2024a), complemented by surface wind velocity data with resolutions of 1 hour and $1/8^\circ$ (CMEMS, 2024b), both provided by the E.U. Copernicus Marine Service. These data sources allowed for an accurate representation of the prevailing oceanographic and atmospheric conditions influencing the vessel’s drift.

- **Object Types:** Given the uncertainties regarding the vessel’s drift characteristics and reported instances of individuals going overboard, we conducted simulations for four different object types: persons in water (PW), a regular skiff (RS), a swamped and capsized skiff (CS), and a fishing vessel (FV). Each object type was designed to replicate characteristic drift behaviours, thereby providing a robust and diverse set of scenarios for analysis.
- **Large Particle Ensemble:** At each of the 17 release points, we deployed 10,000 particles per object type, resulting in a comprehensive drift scenario with a total of 680,000 particles. These particles were tracked continuously until September 4 09:40 UTC, around the estimated time of the Italian Coast Guard’s rescue operation. We chose a time-stepping of 5 minutes for the simulation and 15 minutes for the simulation output. This detailed tracking helped identify likely drift patterns, potential stranding locations and the times when the vessel or its passengers might have entered the Italian SAR zone.

Our approach integrated survivor testimonies with multiple data inputs and enabled us to reconstruct a credible timeline of the vessel’s movements. By simulating drift from various initial positions and conditions, we developed a nuanced understanding of the vessel’s and overboard passengers’ likely drift start and destination, offering valuable insights into the circumstances leading up to the Coast Guard’s rescue operation.

To address our two research questions, we conducted two specific analyses: the interpretation of *probability density heatmaps* and estimations of *average entrance times*. These analyses helped quantify the vessel’s likely drift behaviour and its timing in reaching critical zones around Lampedusa. Below, we briefly describe the methodologies used for each approach.

C. Probability Density Heatmaps

We employed probability density heatmaps to address the first research question - estimating where the vessel would likely have drifted if the engine had stopped shortly after the third sighting. For each of the 17 release positions, labelled from EXT000 to EXT240, we initiated simulations by deploying 10,000 particles per object type, including persons in water, a regular skiff, a swamped and capsized skiff, and a fishing vessel. This approach generated 68 individual heatmaps, i.e. 4 object types $\times$ 17 release positions, each visualising the final distribution of 10,000 particles.

These heatmaps were created separately for each simulation and object type, providing a detailed view of how different objects might drift under the influence of ocean currents and wind. Instead of showing the exact values of the probability densities, we simplified the interpretation by labelling the colour bars with “low”, “medium” and “high” probability densities. This approach helped to clearly indicate areas where particles were more likely to accumulate, representing potential drift destinations.

By focusing on the final distribution of particles at the estimated time of the rescue operation, rather than analysing specific drift paths, the heatmaps allowed us to identify

probable locations where the vessel or associated individuals might have been encountered. This visual analysis across all scenarios enhanced our understanding of the vessel’s likely drift start, drift patterns and the potential vessel locations at the time of rescue.

D. Average Entrance Times

The second research question aimed to determine when the vessel likely entered the Italian SAR zone, the 12 nmi territorial waters and the 5 km radius around the observed helicopter position, referred to as the SAR contour, the 12 nmi contour and the 5 km contour, respectively, as illustrated in Fig. 1. We applied the limits of the Italian Search and Rescue zone as provided by the *Global Integrated Shipping Information System of the International Maritime Organization* (IMO, 2024). We defined the 12 nmi contour around Lampedusa, Lampione and Linosa by applying the *Maritime Boundaries Geodatabase* provided by the *Flanders Marine Institute* (VLIZ, 2023). To conduct our analysis of entrance times, we tracked the trajectories of each simulated particle to identify any entry into these contours during the simulation period.

For each of the 17 simulations and four object types, we recorded the times when particles first crossed the SAR, 12 nmi and 5 km contours. We also calculated the relative number of trajectories entering each contour, providing an initial estimation of the likelihood that a particular simulation reached these critical areas. Using this data, we computed an average entrance time by averaging the entrance times of particles that crossed each contour, offering a consistent metric for evaluating when the vessel or individuals might have initially entered these zones.

We then plotted the average entrance times against the start times of each simulation, corresponding to the extrapolated release points EXT000 to EXT240. Additionally, we displayed the relative number of trajectories entering each contour to evaluate how representative specific average entrance times were. This combined approach enabled us to identify trends in drift timing and assess how different starting conditions influenced the vessel’s entry into the Italian SAR zone, the 12 nmi zone or the 5 km area near the rescue location.

III. RESULTS

A. Final Particle Positions

To address the first research question, we generated heatmaps depicting the probability density of final particle positions. Fig. 2 introduces this approach by first illustrating an example of such final particle positions for simulation EXT075, which simulates a vessel drift starting 75 minutes after the last SB sighting. The particles are coloured by object type, i.e. PW, RS, CS and FV. They are shown alongside key positions and contours, including sightings, the limits of the Italian SAR zone, the 12 nmi boundary and the 5 km rescue area.

Distinct patterns emerge for each object type. RS and CS particles cluster densely, while those for PW and FV are more dispersed. Most RS particles are within the 12 nmi contour south of Lampedusa, with some stranded or bypassing the

Figure 2. EXT075: Final particle positions at 09:40 UTC, September 4. The Lagrangian particle simulation starts at the extrapolated position EXT075 and runs until the estimated time of rescue. Coloured dots represent virtual particles by object type. Key positions, contours, and observations are marked.

island to the northeast. CS particles exhibit a similar concentration, albeit slightly further south. PW particles primarily spread south of Lampedusa, with their highest concentration around the southern limit of the Italian SAR zone. FV particles are the most dispersed and can be found all around the island but rarely in the northwest, with significant numbers inside the SAR contour. Notably, for simulation EXT075, the 5 km rescue area does not coincide with regions of high particle density.

To further analyse these patterns, Fig. 3 aggregates the particle positions to probability density heatmaps, separated by object type. These heatmaps confirm that under the prevailing sea and wind conditions, there is a high probability for RS, CS and FV particles to drift into the Italian SAR zone around Lampedusa. However, PW particles most likely drift towards the southern boundary of the Italian SAR zone, with a moderate but significant likelihood of particles reaching into it. These findings suggest that the vessel and individuals attached to it likely drifted into the Italian SAR zone by the time of the rescue operation. Individuals drifting independently of the vessel movement likely arrived close to the SAR contour, while a significant share of them could have entered the SAR zone.

Moreover, the heatmaps indicate a low likelihood of particles accumulating within the 5 km rescue area. RS and CS particles demonstrate low probability densities within this zone, while PW and FV particles exhibit only low to medium probabilities. Instead, the predominant drift patterns are south and east of the estimated rescue area. Overall, the heatmaps

Figure 3. Probability density heatmaps of final particle positions at 09:40 UTC, September 4, for simulation EXT075. For each object type, the heatmap highlights likely drift destinations.

in Fig. 3 suggest that if the engine ceased around 75 minutes after the last sighting, the objects would have likely arrived south of Lampedusa near the 12 nmi contour, with RS particles drifting closer to the island and FV particles more likely to beach.

We observed similar discrepancies between regions of high particle density and the estimated rescue zone across different simulations. Figs. A.1 to A.5 present similar heatmaps for the simulations starting every full hour after the last SB sighting. As drift start times increase, final high-density areas shift eastward, eventually bypassing the island. Simulations beyond EXT180 show clusters concentrating at Lampedusa’s coast, suggesting an increased likelihood of stranding for PW, RS, and FV types, while CS particles tend to bypass the island. Since the rescue operation has taken place southwest of Lampedusa, this trend implies that the vessel likely began drifting within three hours of the last sighting.

To identify the most representative simulation, we measured the average distance between final particle positions and the estimated rescue location, i.e. the position of the helicopter sighting, across all simulations. Fig. 4 indicates that EXT075 for CS particles yielded the closest match, with the smallest average distance and a comparatively small standard deviation, suggesting this scenario best approximates the actual drift of the vessel, assuming the helicopter observation was representative of the true rescue location. Simulations EXT060 and EXT090 for CS particles yielded the second and third smallest average distances, respectively, confirming the swamped and capsized skiff as the most representative of the four object types.

B. Temporal Analysis of Entry into Critical Zones

For the second research question, we analysed when particles first entered the Italian SAR zone, the 12 nmi zone and the 5 km radius. Fig. 5 shows the average entrance times for the SAR contour across all simulations and object types. We find the latest average entrance times for the CS object type at 01:12 UTC on September 4, with a standard deviation of 06:08 hours. However, this result is associated with simulation EXT000, which corresponds to a drift start at the last sighting time. This scenario conflicts with observations made by the SB crew and reports from witnesses. Furthermore, Figs. 4 and A.1 indicate that EXT000 produces final CS particle

distributions that cluster further away from the estimated rescue location than respective distributions of, for instance, simulations EXT060 and EXT075.

In contrast, we highlight simulation EXT075 for the CS object type, which generates the closest-matching final particle distribution w.r.t. the rescue location. The average entrance time for this scenario is 13:24 UTC on September 3, with a standard deviation of 03:52 hours. This average entrance time derives from 98 % of all particle trajectories, suggesting a reliable estimate for when the particles, and by extension the vessel, likely entered the Italian SAR zone. This significant share of trajectories strengthens the validity of EXT075 as the best-fit simulation of the actual drift pattern. For most of the remaining simulations, the other object types in Fig. 5 demonstrate even earlier average entrance times than the CS type of simulation EXT075. As expected, later release times correspond to earlier entries, as these positions are closer to or within the contour.

Since multiple passengers were reported to have gone overboard and lost, we also evaluated the average entrance times for the person in water (PW) object type of which Fig. 3 presents the final particle distribution. Considering the best-fit particle distribution of simulation EXT075 for the CS vessel type, it is reasonable to infer that the initial instances of passengers going overboard may have occurred around 75 minutes after the last SB sighting. For simulation EXT075, the average entrance time for PW particles into the SAR contour was 11:28 UTC on September 3, with a standard deviation of 07:06 hours, with 63 % of all particle trajectories entering the Italian SAR zone. The high standard deviation is an expression of the distinct dispersion of PW particles that can be observed in Figs. 2 and 3, which was consistent across different simulations. The share of PW particles crossing the SAR contour indicates a moderate but significant probability of independently drifting individuals entering the Italian SAR zone a few hours ahead of the vessel.

The analysis reveals that, across different object types and simulations, the estimated average entry times into the Italian SAR zone were notably earlier than the actual time of the rescue operation, which was recorded at 09:38 UTC on September 4. The same holds for the entry into the 12 nmi territorial waters, for which we present all average entrance times in Fig. A.6 of the appendix. For CS particles

Figure 4. Distances between final particle positions and the observed helicopter position. Each object type’s average distance to the rescue centre is illustrated across all simulations. Green stars and dashed lines indicate the average distance values, shaded bands indicate the respective standard deviation. Red lines highlight the closest match, i.e. the CS particles of simulation EXT075.

Figure 5. Average entrance times for the SAR contour. Each plot displays the distribution of average entrance times across all simulations for a given object type, with the left y-axis showing the entrance time. Dark blue markers and lines represent the average entrance time for each simulation, while shaded bands indicate the standard deviation. The right y-axis in light blue illustrates the relative proportion of particle trajectories that cross the limits of the Italian SAR zone, depicted as a thin, light blue line across simulations. For the RS object type, this proportion remains almost consistently at 100 %.

of simulation EXT075, we estimated an average entrance time of 01:30 UTC on September 4, with a standard deviation of 05:39 hours, with 47 % of all particle trajectories crossing the 12 nmi contour. Given that the rescue operation was conducted *within* territorial waters, we can place great confidence in the particle trajectories that entered the 12 nmi zone and add this entrance time to the timeline of events. Overall, this analysis suggests that the Italian Coast Guard’s rescue operation was launched hours after the vessel had drifted into the Italian SAR zone and subsequently into territorial waters. Individuals who went overboard and were lost close to the moment of drift start might have reached both these zones even before the vessel, see Fig. A.6 for details.

In Fig. A.7, the analysis is extended to the 5 km contour around the estimated rescue location. Previous results have already shown a tendency for particles to accumulate outside this 5 km boundary, and Fig. A.7 confirms this trend. It illustrates low percentages of trajectories crossing the 5 km contour, especially for the CS object type with probabilities close to 0 %. The slight increase in entering particle trajectories for simulations beyond EXT180 can be attributed to the fact that these release positions are situated closer to, or already within, the 5 km area. Therefore, the proximity of these later release points inherently raises the chance of particles drifting through this small area. However, we know that simulations

with particle releases starting near the assumed rescue location likely result in particles stranding on the coast of Lampedusa or bypassing the island on its eastern side, rendering these simulations irrelevant to our study of entrance times.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study aimed to reconstruct the drift patterns of a capsized vessel and persons in water to understand the events surrounding a maritime incident near Lampedusa. Through a detailed analysis of drift simulations, we identified key patterns that help clarify the likely timeline of the vessel’s and its passengers’ movements despite the inherent complexities and uncertainties involved in such reconstructions.

A. Accuracy and Limitations

The accuracy of our findings is influenced by several factors, including uncertainties in helicopter observations, variations in ocean current and wind data, and the parameterisations used to model the drift of different objects. The object types available within the OpenDrift framework should be considered categorical proxies rather than exact representations of the specific object and drift conditions studied here. The discrepancies we identified between the estimated rescue area and regions of high particle density suggest that certain factors may require

further evaluation. However, the consistent patterns observed across multiple simulations and object types lend credibility to our overall approach. Future studies should aim to refine the modelling of this complex scenario, particularly by accounting for different possible moments of capsizing. Employing a broader range of data sources could also enhance the accuracy of future simulations.

B. Key Findings and Implications

Our analysis led to several important findings:

- 1) **Final Vessel Position:** We find that the object type *swamped and capsized skiff (CS)* in simulation EXT075 best reproduces the estimated location of the rescue operation, corresponding to the final vessel position. For these conditions, our results indicate that, by the time of the rescue operation, the vessel had likely drifted south of Lampedusa, within the boundaries of the Italian Search and Rescue zone.
- 2) **Moment of Drift Start:** The dominance of simulation EXT075 suggests that the vessel started drifting approximately 75 minutes after the last Seabird sighting.
- 3) **Entry into Italian SAR Zone and Territorial Waters:** The vessel is estimated to have crossed into the Italian Search and Rescue Zone at approximately 13:24 UTC on September 3 and into territorial waters at approximately 01:30 UTC on September 4, while the Seabird crew identified a rescue time of 09:38 UTC that day. The simulations suggest that the rescue operation by the Italian Coast Guard commenced several hours after the drifting vessel and individuals overboard had likely entered the Italian SAR and the 12 nmi territorial zone.

In conclusion, this study provides critical insights into the incident's likely timeline, like the estimated moment of drift start and the timing in reaching critical zones around Lampedusa. Moreover, our simulations demonstrate the complexity of such drift scenarios. Running drift simulations and launching rescue operations at the first signs of distress can significantly reduce this complexity and save crucial time. These benefits are paramount because every hour counts when lives are at stake.

REFERENCES

C.H. Ainsworth, E.P. Chassignet, D. French-McCay, C.J. Beegle-Krause, I. Berenshtein, J. Englehardt, T. Fiddaman, H. Huang, M. Huettel, D. Justic, V.H. Kourafalou, Y. Liu, C. Mauritzen, S. Murawski, S. Morey, T. Özgökmen, C.B. Paris, J. Ruzicka, S. Saul, J. Shepherd, S. Socolofsky, H. Solo Gabriele, T. Sutton, R.H. Weisberg, C. Wilson, L. Zheng, and Y. Zheng. Ten years of modeling the deep-water horizon oil spill. *Environmental Modelling Software*, 142:105070, 2021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2021.105070>.

CMEMS. Mediterranean sea physics analysis and forecast [dataset]. *E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information (CMEMS), Marine Data Store (MDS)*, 2024a. DOI: https://doi.org/10.25423/CMCC/MEDSEA_

ANALYSISFORECAST_PHY_006_013_EAS8, accessed on 2024-09-18.

CMEMS. Global ocean hourly sea surface wind and stress from scatterometer and model [dataset]. *E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information (CMEMS), Marine Data Store (MDS)*, 2024b. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.48670/moi-00305>, accessed on 2024-09-18.

Knut-Frode Dagestad, Johannes Röhrs, Øyvind Breivik, and Bjørn Ådlandsvik. Opendrift v1.0: a generic framework for trajectory modelling. *Geoscientific Model Development*, 11(4):1405–1420, 2018. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-11-1405-2018>.

Guardia Costiera. Lampedusa, imbarcazione semiaffondata: la guardia costiera salva 7 migranti. *Homepage of the Guardia Costiera Italy*, 2024a. URL: <https://www.guardiacostiera.gov.it/stampa/Pages/Lampedusa-imbarcazione-semiaffondata-la-Guardia-Costiera-salva-7-migranti.aspx>, accessed on 2024-11-08.

Guardia Costiera. Oggi a largo di lampedusa la guardiacostiera ha soccorso 7 migranti a bordo di un'unità alla deriva partita dalla libia. *X (formerly Twitter)*, 2024b. URL: <https://x.com/guardiacostiera/status/1831375344487776708>, accessed on 2024-11-08.

IMO. Rescue Co-ordination Centre / Italy / MRCC Rome / ITA-RCCAreas-807.gml [dataset]. *International Maritime Organization (IMO), Global Integrated Shipping Information System (GISIS)*, 2024. URL: <https://gisis.imo.org/Public/COMSAR/RCC.aspx?CID=ITA&Action=View&ID=807>, accessed on 2024-11-11.

Laurent Lebreton, Boyan Slat, Francesco Ferrari, Bruno Sainte-Rose, Jen Aitken, Robert Marthouse, Sara Hajbane, Serena Cunsolo, Anna Schwarz, Aurore Levivier, et al. Evidence that the great pacific garbage patch is rapidly accumulating plastic. *Scientific Reports*, 8(1):1–15, 2018. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-018-22939-w>.

Rachel D. Simons, David A. Siegel, and Kevin S. Brown. Model sensitivity and robustness in the estimation of larval transport: A study of particle tracking parameters. *Journal of Marine Systems*, 119-120:19–29, 2013. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmarsys.2013.03.004>.

VLIZ. Maritime Boundaries Geodatabase: Territorial Seas (12NM), version 4 [dataset]. *Flanders Marine Institute, Vlaams Instituut voor de Zee (VLIZ)*, 2023. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.14284/633>, accessed on 2024-11-07.

Øyvind Breivik, Arthur A. Allen, Christophe Maisondieu, and Michel Olagnon. Advances in search and rescue at sea. *Ocean Dynamics*, 63:83–88, 2013. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10236-012-0581-1>.

CODE AND DATA AVAILABILITY

Source code, datasets and animations concerning this work can be provided upon request. This study has been conducted using E.U. Copernicus Marine Service Information.

LANGUAGE VERSIONS

Other language versions of this report may exist to facilitate the presentation of the results. However, the English version is authoritative and binding.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

This report was prepared voluntarily by the author, without financial compensation or external funding, at the request of Sea-Watch e.V.. Sea-Watch e.V. contributed to the experiment's design, the report's review, and its translation into Italian. The author also consulted the free versions of the AI tools *ChatGPT*, *Grammarly*, and *DeepL* for assistance in writing and translation.

DISCLAIMER

This work is provided by the copyright holders and contributors "as is" and any express or implied warranties, including but not limited to the implied warranties of merchantability and fitness for a particular purpose are disclaimed. In no event shall the copyright owner or contributors be liable for any direct, indirect, incidental, special, exemplary or consequential damages (including but not limited to procurement of substitute goods or services, loss of use, data or profits, or business interruption) however caused and on any theory of liability, whether in contract, strict liability or tort (including negligence or otherwise) arising in any way out of the use of this work, even if advised of the possibility of such damage.

© 2024 Luca Kunz. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. To view a copy of this

license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>. The report is available online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14084182>.

APPENDIX A: ADDITIONAL FIGURES

Figure A.1. Probability density heatmaps of final particle positions at 09:40 UTC, September 4, for simulation EXT000.

Figure A.2. Probability density heatmaps of final particle positions at 09:40 UTC, September 4, for simulation EXT060.

Figure A.3. Probability density heatmaps of final particle positions at 09:40 UTC, September 4, for simulation EXT120.

Figure A.4. Probability density heatmaps of final particle positions at 09:40 UTC, September 4, for simulation EXT180.

Figure A.5. Probability density heatmaps of final particle positions at 09:40 UTC, September 4, for simulation EXT240.

Figure A.6. Average entrance times for the 12 nmi contour.

Figure A.7. Average entrance times for the 5 km contour.